

Improving the Water Resistance of Bi-Based Perovskite-Inspired Materials for Vapor-Phase Photocatalytic Overall Water Splitting

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Lead halide perovskites are well known for their exceptional photophysical and electronic properties, which have placed them at the forefront of challenging optoelectronic applications and solar-to-fuel conversion. However, their air/water instability, combined with their toxicity, is still a critical problem that has slowed down their commercialization. In this sense, bismuth-based halide derivatives attract much interest as a potentially safer, air-stable alternative. Herein, a novel Bi-based perovskite-inspired material, IEF-19 (IEF stands for IMDEA Energy Framework), which contains a bulky aromatic cation (1,5-diammonium naphthalene), is prepared. Additionally, an *N*-alkylation strategy is successfully employed to achieve four water-stable perovskite-inspired materials, which contains diammonium naphthalene cations that are tetra-alkylated by methyl, ethyl, propyl, and butyl groups. Moreover, computational studies are performed to gain a deeper understanding of the intrinsic structural stability and affinity of water molecules for Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials. Importantly, the air- and water-stable IEF-19-Et (i.e., stable at least 12 months under ambient conditions and 3 weeks in contact with water) is found to be an active photocatalyst for vapor-phase overall water splitting in the absence of any sacrificial agent under both ultraviolet-visible or simulated sunlight irradiation. This material exhibits an estimated apparent quantum yield of 0.08% at 400 nm, partially explained by its adequate energy band level diagram.

1. Introduction

Metal halide perovskites have been efficiently used as light-harvesting materials for a wide range of applications not only in the field of optoelectronic and solar cells,^[1] but also for photocatalysis (including H₂ evolution, CO₂ reduction, organic transformations, and pollutant degradation).^[2–4] Recently, they have also seen use in high-tech applications such as information display systems, functional integration systems, electronic communication systems, and health and medical systems.^[5] In particular, lead halide perovskite materials are commonly investigated due to their outstanding optoelectronic properties. Nevertheless, these materials are sensitive to environmental and operating conditions such as oxygen, humidity, UV light irradiation, and high temperature,^[6] limiting their use in industrial applications. Depending on the moisture amount, the water-perovskite interaction can trigger

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different processes:^[7] 1) hydration (i.e., formation of hydrogen bonds between water and organic cation), 2) decomposition (caused by the accumulation of water molecules), or 3) dissolution (associated with the decomposition process). In this regard, various strategies have been used to improve the moisture stability in perovskite materials such as 1) the formation of core-shell structures,^[8] 2) compositional engineering,^[9] and 3) the anchoring hydrophobic polymers,^[10] among others.

Bismuth-based halide derivatives, which possess potential photophysical properties (including tunable bandgaps, high charge carrier mobility, and large absorption coefficients),^[11] have emerged as a less toxic and more air-stable alternative to Pb-based perovskites.^[12–14] However, Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials tend to decompose easily in aqueous solutions due to their ionic nature, and they perform only optimally in organic solvents and hydrohalic acid solutions.^[15] This fact has limited their use in aqueous photocatalytic applications,^[16] since the hydrolysis of these materials can easily lead to the formation of BiOI.^[15] Consequently, the development of robust and water-stable perovskite-based photocatalysts represents an exceptional challenge. In this regard, Liu et al.^[17] reported a promising solvothermal route (140 °C for 3 days) based on the *in situ* *N*-ethyl alkylation of the organic cation, a hydrogen-bond-free synthesis strategy. This reaction resulted in a water-stable perovskite-inspired material, Etb₂Bi₂I₁₀, with a yield of 42%. This material was proposed as photocatalyst for H₂ evolution in an acid medium (HI/H₃PO₂), achieving 6.8 μmol of H₂ after 5 h. The synthesis of the Me₄ppi-BiI₄ (Me₄ppi = 1-methyl-4-phenylpyridin-1-ium) was also performed via *in situ* *N*-methyl alkylation (120 °C for 3 days), though with a low yield (26%). This significantly improved its stability compared to the non-alkylated derivative.^[18] Recently, Li et al. also reported the synthesis of the perovskite-inspired material (Me₃TMP)Bi₂I₉ (Me₃TMP = (1,1',1''-(benzene-1,3,5-triyl)tris(3-methyl-1 H-imidazol-3-ium))) at 120 °C for 4 days, resulting in a yield of 20%. This material contains a classic hydrogen-bond-free cation, which resulted in an enhanced thermal and moisture stability, even upon complete immersion in water, making it suitable for applications in thermistors.^[19]

For first time, we recently reported efficient photocatalytic vapor-phase overall water splitting (OWS) over robust bismuth-based perovskite-inspired materials (named IEF-15, IEF-16, and IEF-17; IEF stands for IMDEA Energy Framework). In this work, to enhance both the stability of these Bi-based materials and their H₂ photocatalytic performance, we propose two strategies: 1) the use of a conjugated diammonium cation that may establish cations- π and π - π interactions to improve the water stability of the material^[20] and 2) the *in situ* alkylation of the diammonium cation to avoid the formation of hydrogen bonds with external water molecules.^[21] The first strategy resulted in the formation of a novel perovskite-inspired material based on Bi³⁺ and 1,5-diammoniumnaphthalene cations, denoted IEF-19. It is reported that the presence of conjugated π -cations in lead-based perovskites can improve the band alignment between the organic and inorganic components, enhancing the electronic interactions between the layers.^[22] The combination of both strategies led to the construction of four structures with different *N*-alkyl chain length (named IEF-19-R; where R = Me, Et, Pr, and But representing an *N*-methylated, ethylated, propylated, and butylated

diammonium cation, respectively). For the first time, we investigate the influence of the length of the *N*-alkyl chain on the optoelectronic properties of Bi-based hybrid perovskites and their water stability using experimental characterization techniques. Additional insights into the intrinsic material and water stability are provided through computational studies. In summary, this work presents several innovative points: 1) the development of a series of five new Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials; 2) the demonstration of the remarkable stability of IEF-19-Et in water; 3) the combination of experimental and computational studies to fully understand structure and stability of the new material; 4) the achievement of high-photocatalytic H₂ production via OWS of the IEF-19-Et material, surpassing other perovskite-inspired photocatalysts; and 5) the improved cyclability of photocatalytic activity of IEF-19-Et.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Synthesis and Characterization of the Bismuth-Based Perovskite-Inspired Materials

The 1D nanostructures are recognized as effective components for improving solar-powered catalytic technologies due to their short charge diffusion length.^[23] In this study, we prepared a 1D novel hybrid bismuth iodine (IEF-19), which contains a π -conjugated molecule as organic cation (1,5 diammonium naphthalene cation), using a facile synthetic method (25 °C, 1 h). As a second strategy to improve its water stability, we fabricated four *N*-alkylated derivatives (IEF-19-R, being R = Me, Et, Pr, and But) using a more time-efficient solvothermal approach (150 °C, 12 h vs 120 °C, 72–96 h in reported works) and achieving yields superior to those previously reported (67%–83% vs 20%–42%).^[15–17] Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) patterns of the resulting materials compared to simulated ones confirmed the formation of pure phases in all cases (see Figure S1, Supporting Information).

Single-crystal X-ray diffraction (SCXRD) analysis for IEF-19 revealed that the material crystallizes with one methanol molecule per unit formula, forming I...H–N hydrogen bonds with the *N*-protonated organic cations (Table S1, Supporting Information, and Figure 1). The structure contains anionic (Bi₂I₈)_n 1D chains with edge-sharing BiI₆ centers, which are linked in *cis* and *trans* positions (Figure 1). The bismuth has a distorted octahedral coordination geometry with Bi–I distances ranging from 2.934(2) to 3.253(1) Å. The Bi...Bi separation between adjacent subunits varies in the range 4.6289(16)–4.6318(16) Å (Table S2, Supporting Information). The I–Bi–I angles in *cis* position oscillate from 82.19(3)° to 96.99(4)°, and those in *trans* position vary from 168.21(4)° to 175.68(4)° (see Table S3, Supporting Information). The organic cations are located along the *a* axis and are perpendicular to the inorganic chain (see Figure 1), forming I...H–N hydrogen bonds and I...H–C interactions that range from 2.7065(15) to 3.1687(15) Å. A remarkable observation is the short separation between adjacent inorganic chains, resulting in I...I distances of 4.0710(19) Å, which are only slightly larger than the van der Waals interaction (3.9 Å).^[24]

The structures of the alkylated derivatives IEF-19-Me, IEF-19-Et, and IEF-19-Pr are also composed of anionic (Bi₂I₈)_n 1D chains with edge-sharing BiI₆ centers (Figure 2a–c). The cationic N¹, N¹,

Figure 1. Structure of IEF-19 (Bi, I, O, N, C, and H atoms correspond to orange, purple, red, blue, brown, and pink ellipsoids, respectively).

N^5, N^5 -tetra-alkyl-1,5-diammonium naphthalene molecules were found in the interlayer space forming weak I...H–C bonds with the anionic chains. The Bi–I bond distances for IEF-19-R (R = Me, Et, and Pr; Table S4–S9, Supporting Information) range from 2.8989(8) to 3.3483(6) Å. In contrast, the structure of IEF-19-But comprises anionic Bi_4I_{16} clusters with two diammonium naphthalene cations (Figure 2d). The $[Bi_4I_{16}]^{4-}$ anion is formed by four distorted BiI_6 octahedra, which contain three types of iodine coordination: terminal (μ_1 -I), triply bridging (μ_3 -I), and double bridging (μ_2 -I). As expected, the Bi– μ_3 -I distances are larger (3.3332(6)–3.4230(6) Å) compared to Bi– μ_2 -I (3.0376(6)–3.4480(9) Å), and Bi– μ_1 -I distances (2.8615(10)–2.8883(9) Å; Table S10 and S11, Supporting Information). The organic cations are located in the space between the anionic clusters, forming I...H–N hydrogen bonds (2.7279 Å). Note that the tetra-alkylation of the diammonium cation is crystallographically confirmed in all cases.

In addition, Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra for Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials were collected and compared to that of organic free ligand (DAN; see Figure S2, Supporting Information). In the spectrum of DAN, the strong bands at 3410 – 3220 cm^{-1} are attributed to the NH_2 groups and those at 1625 – 1514 cm^{-1} to aromatic rings. Upon incorporating the organic compound into the material, N–H vibrations show a significant shift at around 3500 cm^{-1} , confirming the protonation of the amine group. Also, the C–H vibrations of the aromatic ring and C–H vibrations of alkyl groups are observed at around 2960 and 3100 cm^{-1} , respectively. Regarding the optical properties, the bandgap values of these novel perovskite-inspired materials were estimated using Tauc plots from ultraviolet–visible (UV–vis) diffuse reflectance measurements, assuming a direct bandgap (see Figure S3, Supporting Information). All the synthesized materials exhibited similar bandgap values: 2.1 eV for IEF-19, IEF-19-Me, and IEF-19-Et, and 2.2 eV for IEF-19-Pr and IEF-19-But. These values are in accordance with those observed for other reported Bi-based inspired-perovskite materials.^[11] Similarly, the as-prepared materials display an emission band close to the absorption edge at 630 nm (excitation at 405 nm; Figure S4, Supporting Information), confirming that they are direct semiconductors.

2.2. Thermal and Water Stability

Hydrothermal/solvothermal methods are frequently used as an efficient strategy to prepare crystalline and stable lead-free perovskite-inspired photocatalysts.^[25] For example, Krishnaiah et al.^[26] prepared the lead-free material Cs_2SnI_6 using an optimized hydrothermal method, resulting in a thermally stable photodetector (>100 °C). A solvothermal method was employed by Zhao et al.^[27] achieving millimeter-size $[(CH_3)_2NH_2]_3[BiI_6]$ crystals. This material exhibited a superior H_2 evolution activity by photocatalytic splitting of HI compared to powdered $[(CH_3)_2NH_2]_3[BiI_6]$. Also, the bismuth-based double-halide $MA_3Bi_2Cl_{9-x}I_x$ with a bandgap funnel structure was obtained by a solvothermal method. This resulted in an enhanced H_2 generation rate due to improved migration of photoinduced charge transfer from the interior to the surface.^[28] In this work, the thermal stability of the as-prepared Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials was examined by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), temperature-dependent PXRD (TD-PXRD). Further insights into the thermal stability are provided by computational studies. By comparing the TGA curves (Figure 3), IEF-19-Et demonstrates superior thermal robustness, with a decomposition temperature exceeding 200 °C. In contrast, IEF-19-But exhibits poor thermal stability, decomposing at 100 °C. Moreover, in the TGA plot of IEF-19, a gradual weight loss is observed from 70 °C, corresponding to the loss of methanol molecules, which are bound by hydrogen bonds to organic ligands. This is consistent with the TD-PXRD analysis of IEF-19 (Figure S5a, Supporting Information), revealing the appearance of a new peak at 9.3° (from 70 °C), which could be attributed to structural changes associated to the methanol departure. TD-PXRD studies of the N-alkylated derivatives indicate that IEF-19-Me and IEF-19-Et are the most thermally robust materials (i.e., complete decomposition at 210 °C; Figure S5b,c, Supporting Information), while IEF-19-Pr degrades at lower temperature (190 °C). As observed by TGA, IEF-19-But is the material with the lowest thermal stability, showing significant structural changes at 100 °C (Figure S5d, Supporting Information). Note that the novel perovskite-inspired materials exhibit greater thermal stability (especially IEF-19, IEF-19-Me, and IEF-19-Et), surpassing that

Figure 2. Structures of the alkylated derivatives: a) IEF-19-Me, b) IEF-19-Et, c) IEF-19-Pr, and d) IEF-19-But (Bi, I, N, C, and H atoms correspond to orange, purple, blue, brown, and pink ellipsoids, respectively).

Figure 3. TGA curves of Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials.

of the extensively studied $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ perovskite (also known as MAPbI_3), which decomposes at 90°C .^[29]

The water stability of the bismuth-iodine hybrid materials was investigated under both static and stirring conditions. The static condition experiments were carried out by completely immersing the bulky material in water for 3 days (IEF-19) and 3 weeks (the alkylated derivatives; **Figure 4**, S6, Supporting Information). As can be seen in **Figure 4**, the alkylated derivatives exhibit enhanced water stability compared to non-alkylated one (IEF-19), either partially or totally maintaining their intact structure. The PXRD pattern of IEF-19 reveals a complete hydrolysis and transformation into BiOI (peaks at 9.6° , 29.6° , and 31.6° ; see **Figure S6a**, Supporting Information), within only 3 days, confirming its poor water stability. In contrast, additional diffraction peaks can be seen in the IEF-19-Me sample after 3 weeks, as ascribed to the partial hydrolysis of the material and the formation of BiOI (**Figure S6b**, Supporting Information). For IEF-19-Pr, only a slight BiOI fraction appears in the PXRD pattern after 3 weeks (**Figure S6d**, Supporting Information). The PXRD of IEF-19-But displays some variations, such as the reduced intensity of the peak at 6.7° , and the emergence of two new peaks at

Figure 4. Comparison of PXRD patterns of Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials after static immersion in water for 3 days (IEF-19) or 3 weeks (the alkylated perovskite derivatives), and the standard BiOI sample (JCPDS no. 10-0445).

6.6° and 6.8° (**Figure S6e**, Supporting Information), which may be due to an internal rearrangement of isolated tetramers (Bi_4I_{16}). Note that the crystalline structure of the IEF-19-Et remains intact for at least 3 weeks (**Figure S6c**, Supporting Information), proving to be the most water-stable material among the as-prepared Bi-based materials. Further, in comparison with other reported systems, the lead-based perovskite $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ transforms to $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{I}$, PbI_2 , and $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_4\text{PbI}_6 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ after being immersed in water for 30 s. In contrast, the hybrid $\text{EtbtBi}_2\text{I}_{10}$ is water stable for at least 7 days^[30] while the hybrid $(\text{H}_3\text{TMP})\text{BiI}_6$ suffers structural changes within 14 days in water.^[19]

The water stability was also examined by suspending the bismuth-based materials in water under stirring for 2 and 5 h (**Figure S7**, Supporting Information). Upon these conditions, the PXRD patterns of IEF-19 and IEF-19-Me exhibit characteristic peaks attributed to the formation of BiOI (peaks at 9.6° , 29.6° , and 31.6° ; **Figure S7a,b**, Supporting Information). In the case of IEF-19-Pr and IEF-19-But, the patterns only show a small diffraction peak at 31.6° , which became more intense after 5 h (**Figure S7d,e**, Supporting Information), indicating that these materials are more hydrolytically stable than IEF-19 and IEF-19-Me. It is important to highlight that the diffraction patterns of IEF-19-Et do not show significant changes (**Figure S7c**, Supporting Information), further confirming its exceptional robustness. In addition, IEF-19-Et remains stable for at least 12 months under long-term exposure to ambient conditions (**Figure S8**, Supporting Information), demonstrating its high air and moisture stability.

2.3. Computational Studies

For more insights into the robustness of the Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials, we investigate two types of material stability using DFT calculations: 1) the structural stability and 2) the water stability. Together these two types of studies provide insights into the material stability under operating conditions, such as high temperatures or contact with water.

To assess the structural stability of the structures, we probe the strength of the I...H–N hydrogen bonds between the organic cations and the inorganic Bi-based framework by calculating the bond order and analyzing the bond geometry. Specifically, we investigate the I...H bond order (BO_{HB}), I...H bond distance (d_{HB}), and I...H–N bond angle (θ_{HB}) in DFT-optimized geometries. In **Table 1**, the comparison of bond orders indicate that

Table 1. Characteristics of I...H–N hydrogen bonds between DAN cations and inorganic framework in Bi-based perovskite-inspired material. The overview includes bond order (BO_{HB}), bond distance (d_{HB}), and bond angle (θ_{HB}) of the hydrogen bonds.

Material	BO_{HB} [–]	d_{HB} [Å]	θ_{HB} [°]
IEF-19	0.14	2.52	162.3
IEF-19-Me	0.11	2.58	146.1
IEF-19-Et	0.08	2.71	143.6
IEF-19-Pr	0.09	2.67	144.0
IEF-19-But	0.09	2.67	147.3

hydrogen bonds are substantially weaker for Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials in which the cations are substituted with large side groups (i.e., IEF-19-R with R = Et, Pr and But), resulting in bond orders in the range of 0.08–0.09, compared to cations with no or small side groups (i.e., IEF-19 and IEF-19-Me) where the bond orders range from 0.11 to 0.14. We highlight that this decrease in the hydrogen bond strength for perovskite-inspired material with bulky side groups on the cations could be related to changes in the geometry of the hydrogen bonds. Not only do the hydrogen bonds become longer (from 2.52 to 2.71 Å), they also exhibit a larger deviation from the typical ideal hydrogen bond angle of 180° (from 162.3 to 143.6°), which explains the weakening of the bonds. As a result of the weaker hydrogen bonds, bonds between inorganic framework and organic cations are more readily broken as a result of temperature effects, thus significantly impacting the material stability. Moreover, we note that the different mode of packing for IEF-19-But (clusters) compared to the other IEF-19-R compounds (chains) also negatively impacts the material structural stability. Together the hydrogen bonds strength and overall packing in the Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials indicate why materials with smaller side groups are most stable under thermal stress.

The reactivity of the Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials with water was examined using the deprotonation enthalpies of the various *N*-alkylated organic cations. Enthalpies for deprotonation were calculated for the loss of the first proton (ΔE_1) and second proton (ΔE_2) using the following reaction mechanism for the DAN cations:

where the first and second reaction scheme indicate the loss of the first and second proton. An overview of the various DAN cations is shown in Figure S9, Supporting Information. The results in Table 2 indicate that it is more difficult for the organic cations to deprotonate when substituted with longer alkyl chains. Noticeably, for the loss of the first proton (ΔE_1), the non-substituted cation in IEF-19 (−0.98 eV) and the cation in IEF-19-Me (−0.09 eV) possess a negative deprotonation, indicating a high tendency for deprotonation reactions. In contrast, the cations with large side groups (i.e., cations in IEF-19-R with R = Et, Pr, and But) have positive deprotonation enthalpies ranging from +0.46 to +0.68 eV. For the loss of the second proton, a similar

Table 2. Deprotonation enthalpy for DAN cations. The deprotonation enthalpies for the loss of the first proton (ΔE_1) and second proton (ΔE_2) are provided.

Material	ΔE_1 [eV]	ΔE_2 [eV]
IEF-19	−0.98	+ 2.36
IEF-19-Me	−0.09	+ 3.01
IEF-19-Et	+ 0.46	+ 3.24
IEF-19-Pr	+ 0.62	+ 3.31
IEF-19-But	+ 0.68	+ 3.34

trend of increasing deprotonation energies for larger side groups is found, albeit with significantly larger energies ($\Delta E_2 > 2$ eV). This trend in deprotonation enthalpies can be explained by the inductive effects of the alkyl side groups. The electron donating character of the alkyl side groups results in a larger electron density on the N atom, which makes it harder for the N–H bonds to break. Therefore, the alkyl side groups increase the basicity of the organic cations an effect seen in other aromatic amines,^[31] inhibiting their ability to lose protons. The effect is larger for longer alkyl chains, explaining the trend of increasing deprotonation energies. The loss of either one or two protons in a cation hinders the ability of organic cations to form hydrogen bonds, thus limiting the water stability of the perovskite-inspired materials that are prone to deprotonation.

2.4. Photocatalytic Vapor-Phase OWS

The most water stable IEF-19-Et material was tested as photocatalyst for vapor-phase OWS under both UV–vis and simulated sunlight irradiation. As can be seen in Figure 5a, H₂ production rate under UV–vis light is noticeably higher than that observed during irradiation with simulated sunlight (89 vs 19 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ at 24 h). The simulated sunlight contains mainly visible and IR light, with only a minor contribution of about 5% of UV photons in the UVA region. This suggests that even though the UV–vis absorption spectrum of IEF-19-Et is characterized by a strong absorption from 200 to about 550 nm (Figure 5b), most of the photoresponse of the material originates from UV light. However, IEF-19-Et exhibits a superior H₂ production for OWS under simulated sunlight irradiation (8.3 $\mu\text{mol g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$ at 5 h) compared to that observed for other reported hybrid materials: MAPbI₃/MA⁺ membrane H₂ evolution rate = 0.313 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ at 1 h in a HI medium,^[32] EtbBi₂I₁₀ H₂ evolution rate = 6.8 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ at 5 h in an acid medium,^[17] IEF-16 H₂ production rate = 3.5 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ at 3 h in vapor-phase OWS,^[33] and DMASnI₃ H₂ evolution rate = 0.64 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ in deionized water.^[34]

The efficiency of the photocatalytic activity for OWS was quantified using the apparent quantum yield (AQY) with monochromatic light at 400 and 450 nm, resulting in AQY values of 0.08% and 0.02%, respectively. It is consistent with a previous observation of higher photocatalytic performance at shorter wavelengths. Surprisingly, it is worth noting that a fourfold decrease in AQY values occurs from 400 to 450 nm, even though optical absorption is slightly higher at 450 nm (see Figure 5b). Furthermore, the reusability of IEF-19-Et in OWS was tested over three additional cycles (96 h), keeping its H₂ activity for up to four cycles (20.0% ± 1.5%, 18.8% ± 1.8%, 17.2% ± 1.7%, and 17.7 ± 1.8 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$, for the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th cycle, respectively). It is important to highlight that IEF-19-Et demonstrates excellent water and photochemical stability. Thus, IEF-19-Et maintains its crystalline structure unaltered after three cycles with only a slight decrease in crystallinity after four cycles (Figure S10, Supporting Information).

To gain more information about the photocatalytic performance of IEF-19-Et sample, transient photocurrent measurements were carried out. This sample was supported on a transparent fluorinated tin oxide (FTO) electrode. Figure S11,

Figure 5. a) Hydrogen production for OWS reaction at different times, using UV–vis irradiation (blue) with an AM 1.5 G light filter (red). b) UV–vis diffuse reflectance spectrum of IEF-19-Et, with the AQY (%) obtained at 400 and 450 nm. c) Reusability testing of IEF-19-Et after three 24 h cycles with an AM 1.5 G light filter. d) Mass spectrometry data of gas samples after a 24 h experiment.

Supporting Information, shows the photocurrent response of IEF-19-Et sample, acting as a working electrode upon polarization at +0.4 V and using an aqueous solution of Na₂SO₄ as an electrolyte. The photocurrent response of this sample is over five times higher under UV–vis irradiation compared to simulated sunlight illumination. These observations are consistent with the superior photocatalytic response of IEF-19-Et during vapor-phase OWS under UV–vis irradiation, as compared to experiments using simulated sunlight.

When performing OWS, an important point is to provide a firm confirmation that the evolved oxygen is derived from water rather than other potential impurities in the system. To provide this experimental support, photocatalytic OWS was carried out with labeled H₂¹⁸O, and the headspace vapor was analyzed by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) spectrometry. In this spectrum (Figure 5d), one can observe the presence of Ar (m/z 40), H₂¹⁸O (m/z 20), and some air (N₂ m/z 28 and O₂ m/z 32 in a proportion of 5 to 1), as well as a peak at m/z 36, which is expected for ¹⁸O₂. Note that the lack of a peak at m/z 34 indicates an absence of scrambling between labeled and unlabeled oxygen during the analysis. This result clearly demonstrates H₂¹⁸O as the source ¹⁸O₂.

3. Conclusions

In this work, we have successfully prepared thermally and water-stable Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials for aqueous photocatalytic applications. Employing a conjugated diammonium cation and an *N*-alkylation synthetic strategy (150 °C, 12 h, and 67–83% yields), five novel structures were efficiently synthesized containing non-alkylated (IEF-19) or tetra-alkylated diammonium naphthalene cations by methyl, ethyl, propyl, and butyl groups (denoted IEF-19-Me, IEF-19-Et, IEF-19-Pr, and IEF-19-But, respectively). Empirical characterization revealed that IEF-19-Et exhibits the highest thermal (>200 °C) and longer-term water stability (3 weeks in water), among the synthesized materials. Further insights into the water stability of the Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials were provided through computational studies. They highlighted the role of longer alkyl side chains in increasing the water stability of the perovskite-inspired materials by providing the organic cations with a higher basicity, thus making them less prone to deprotonation. Furthermore, IEF-19-Et demonstrated to be a robust photocatalyst for vapor-phase OWS in absence of sacrificial agents, reaching about 90 and 20 μmol g⁻¹ at 24 h under UV–vis and

simulated sunlight irradiation, respectively. Moreover, IEF-19-Et maintained its H₂ activity for at least four 24 h cycles (96 h). Its exceptional water and photochemical stability make it suitable for photocatalytic water applications.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: Reagents and solvents were commercially sourced and used without further purification. Bismuth (III) nitrate pentahydrate (Bi(NO₃)₃·5H₂O, 98%) and hydroiodic acid (HI, 57% wt. solution) were purchased from ACROS Organics. Bismuth (III) oxide nanopowder (Bi₂O₃, >99%) and 1,5-diaminonaphthalene (DAN, 97%) were acquired from Alfa Aesar and Sigma-Aldrich, respectively. Absolute ethanol was obtained from J.T. Baker. Methanol, n-propanol, and n-butanol (HPLC grade, 99.5%) were purchased from Labkem.

Synthesis of IEF-19: An amount of 1 mmol (486 mg) of Bi(NO₃)₃·5H₂O was added to 5 mL of methanol in a round flask under stirring. After 10 min, 4.5 mmol (0.6 mL, 57 wt% aqueous solution) of HI was added, followed by the addition of 5 mL of a 0.1 M solution of 1,5-diaminonaphthalene (DAN) in methanol and stirring 1 h at room temperature. Then, the resulting solid was filtered, washed several times with diethyl ether, and dried under nitrogen. Red single crystals were grown by through evaporation of methanol at room temperature. C₁₂H₂₀Bi₂l₈N₂O₂: yield: 72.8%; calculated (%): C, 8.70; N, 1.69; and H, 1.22; found (%): C, 8.48; N, 1.89; and H, 1.17.

Synthesis of the N-Alkylated Derivatives (IEF-19-Me, IEF-19-Et, IEF-19-Pr, and IEF-19-But): To synthesize the N-alkylated derivatives, IEF-19-Me, IEF-19-Et, IEF-19-Pr, or IEF-19-But, 1 mmol (0.466 mg) of Bi₂O₃, 1 mmol (0.158 mg) of DAN, and 12.1 mmol (1.6 mL, 57 wt% aqueous solution) of HI were added in a stainless-steel Teflon-lined reactor, followed by adding 10 mL of methanol, ethanol, propanol, or butanol, respectively. Then, the reactor was sealed and heated at 150 °C for 12 h with a ramp of 1 °C min⁻¹. The resulting crystals were washed with diethyl ether and dried under N₂. IEF-19-Me: yield 83.3%. C₁₄H₂₀Bi₂l₈N₂: calculated (%): C, 10.19; N, 1.70; and H, 1.22; found (%): C, 10.67; N, 1.84; and H, 1.84. IEF-19-Et: yield: 83.8%. C₁₈H₂₈Bi₂l₈N₂: calculated (%): C, 12.68; N, 1.64; and H, 1.65; found (%): C, 12.19; N, 1.68; and H, 1.42. IEF-19-Pr: yield: 67.5%. C₂₂H₃₂Bi₂l₈N₂: calculated (%): C, 15.03; N, 1.59; and H, 1.84; found (%): C, 14.08; N, 1.69; and H, 1.80. IEF-19-But: yield: 71.5%. C₂₂H₃₂Bi₂l₈N₂: calculated (%): C, 17.18; N, 1.54; and H, 2.44; found (%): C, 17.64; N, 1.63; and H, 2.41.

Water Stability Studies: For static experiments, 30 mg of the sample was dispersed in 4 mL of Milli-Q water and left for either 3 days or 3 weeks. After this period, the solid was separated by centrifugation and then dried at 40 °C for 2 h. For experiments under stirring, a similar protocol was followed, but the dispersion was stirred (250 rpm) for 2 and 5 h.

Computational Studies: The bulk crystals were investigated using density-functional theory (DFT) calculations with the projector-augmented wave method as implemented in the Vienna Ab initio Simulation Package.^[35–37] The exchange–correlation (XC) interactions of the electrons were modeled with the Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof (PBE) functional^[38] using the Becke–Johnson damped DFT-D3 scheme^[39] for the dispersive interactions. The outermost electrons of H (1s¹), C (2s²2p²), N (2s²2p³), O (2s²2p⁴), I (5s²5p⁵), and Bi (6s²6p³) were treated as valence electrons. The plane wave basis set was expanded to 500 eV. I-centered *k* meshes with a spacing of 0.03 × 2π Å⁻¹ were used to sample the reciprocal space, the resulting *k* meshes are found in Table S12, Supporting Information. The bulk structures were optimized by allowing the atomic positions to change, while keeping the cell shape and volume fixed to that of the experimental geometry. During the structural optimization, electronic and force convergence criterion of 10⁻⁵ eV and 10⁻² eV Å⁻¹ were used. Bond orders were computed using the DDEC6 charge partitioning scheme.^[40,41]

For the investigation of the organic cations, we carried out DFT calculations with ADFF^[42,43] using AMS2022 (SCM Software for Chemistry & Materials). For all atomic species (H, C, N, and O), all electrons were

treated as valence electrons using Slater-type orbitals with a TZP basis set.^[44] The XC interactions of the electrons were modeled using the PBE functional,^[38] explicitly treating the dispersive interactions with the DFT-D3(BJ) scheme.^[39] Relativistic effects were included using the zero-order regular approximated hamiltonian.^[45]

General Instrumentation: PXRDs were collected from 5° to 55° (2θ) using an Empyrean (PANALYTICAL) diffractometer, which was equipped with a PIXce3D detector and operated at 45 kV and 40 mA. A CuKα (Niβ filter, λ = 1.5406 Å) radiation source was utilized. TD X-ray diffraction patterns were acquired with a D8 Advance (Bruker AXS) θ–2θ diffractometer, with a CuKα radiation source (λ = 1.5406 Å) and an LYNXEYE XE detector. Samples were heated from 30 to 270 °C in an Anton Paar XRK 900 chamber under Ar at 50 mL min⁻¹. FTIR spectra were recorded on a Thermo Scientific Nicolet 6700 spectrophotometer in attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode (ATR-FTIR), using 32 accumulations per scan. Diffuse reflectance UV–vis spectra were acquired with a Perkin Elmer LAMBDA 1050 UV–vis spectrophotometer and using BaSO₄ as a reference standard. Bandgap values (E_g) were determined by using the Kubelka–Munk function. Photoluminescence spectra were recorded on a F55 fluorescence spectrophotometer (Edinburgh instruments) using a Xe lamp at 405 nm. TGAs were conducted using a Q600 analyzer (TA Instruments), from 25 to 400 °C (5 °C min⁻¹) under Ar.

SCXRD: SCXRD data were collected at 100 K (IEF-19-Me, IEF-19-Et) and room temperature (IEF-19, IEF-19-Pr, and IEF-19-But) on a Bruker D8 Venture diffractometer using Mo Kα (λ = 0.71073 Å) equipped with a PHOTON 3 detector and an Oxford cryo-system. Data were collected and processed using APEX III software. An adsorption correction was applied using SADABS software through empirical methods measuring symmetry equivalent reflections at different azimuthal angles. All structures were solved using the SHELXT program and refined using least squares refinement methods on all F₂ values as implemented within SHELXL^[46]. Both SHELXT and SHELXL were operated through the Olex2 (v1.5) interface.^[47] All atoms were anisotropically refined and the atomic displacement parameters were refined with suitable restraints or constraints to keep them physically reasonable. Hydrogen atoms were placed in calculated positions and refined with idealized geometries, assigned fixed occupancies, and isotropic displacement parameters. Diammonium naphthalene cations were disordered and modeled over two sites. The C–C and C–N bond distances were restrained to be similar using SHELXL SADI restraints. The atomic displacement parameters were also restrained to be similar using SIMU SHELXL restraints. Crystallographic data are included in Table S1, Supporting Information.

Crystal structures were deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre as supplementary publication numbers CCDC 2341 806–2 341 810. Copies of the data could be obtained free of charge on application to the Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax: +44-1223-335 033; e-mail: deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

Photocatalytic Vapor-Phase OWS: The experiments were performed in a 30 mL glass reactor, which was equipped with an inner cup having a diameter of 0.8 cm, positioned in the middle of the reactor. An amount of 5 mg of the IEF-19-Et was placed in the reactor, ensuring that it remained isolated from any liquid water. Prior to the reaction, the reactor was purged with argon gas and then pressurized to 0.9 bar. For UV–vis experiments, the Bi-based photocatalyst was irradiated using a Hamamatsu light system. This system was equipped with a Hg–Xe 150 W bulb and optic fiber (Hamamatsu spotlight source L9566-04 and light guide A10014-50-0110). For simulated sunlight irradiation, an AM 1.5 G light filter (Lasing ref. 81 094) was placed between the photoreactor and the optic fiber. Gas samples were analyzed using an Agilent 490 MicroGC, which was equipped with two channels. The channel equipped with thermal conductivity detector allowed the detection and quantification of H₂ and O₂, using a MolSieve 5 A column.

Chronoamperometry experiments were carried out using a Gamry potentiostat in a three-neck cell, with an Ag/AgCl 1 M NaCl reference electrode and a 0.5 cm diameter graphite disc as a counter electrode. Photocurrent densities were measured using a 0.05 M Na₂SO₄ electrolyte in water, applying a potential of 0.4 V versus the reference electrode. The photoelectrode was made by depositing a thin film of IEF-19-Et onto a

FTO-transparent electrode through doctor blade technique. The paste used for deposition was prepared by suspending 10 mg of the sample in 1 mL of hexane, adding 150 μ L of α -terpineol, and then heating the suspension with stirring at 60 $^{\circ}$ C until all the hexane was evaporated, obtaining a dense and viscous paste.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

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